

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE KIPCHAK MIGRATION TO THE CAUCASUS

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Abstract

Nomadic tribes of Turkic origin, known as Kipchaks, left a deep mark in the history of the steppe regions of Eurasia, and had a serious impact on the development of Eastern European states. The Kipchaks participated in the ethnogenesis of most of the current Turkic peoples, including the Azerbaijani Turkic.

Turkic tribes of Kipchaks also actively participated in the formation of a number of nations. Among the numerous Turkic peoples, in the formation of which the Kipchaks participated, it is possible to mention the Kazakhs, Kyrgyz, Karakalpak, Turkmen, Tatars, Bashkir, Altai and other peoples of the Northern Caucasus (Nogay, Karachay, Balkar). This also testifies to the great role of the Kipchaks in the formation of these nations. Kipchak ethnic elements were also included in the composition of Ottoman Turkic, Azerbaijanis, Hungarians and other nations.

Keywords: The Turkic tribes, Kipchak, Origin, Migration, Caucasus, Russia, Eurasian steppes.

Introduction

Kipchaks are Turkic nomadic tribes that played a significant role in the history of the Eurasian steppes. Starting from the 9th-10th centuries, they gradually occupied vast territories from the Irtysh and Altai to the Black Sea, forming a powerful military-political union, known in Russian and Eastern sources as the Polovtsy, and in Western European sources as the Kumans. Their mobile nomadic way of life, developed military organization and active participation in trade made the Kipchaks one of the key peoples of the steppe world of the Middle Ages. Interacting with Russia, Byzantium, Khorezm and other states of the region, they had a significant impact on the political processes and cultural exchange of that time. The history of the Kipchaks became an important part of the formation of the ethnic map of modern Turkic peoples, including Kazakh, Karachay, Balkars and others.

1. Questions about Origin

The word "Kipchak" is first mentioned in the work of the Chinese historian Sima Qian, "Historical Notes." In this work, he mentions the names of five tribes that were part of the Asian Huns: Hongyu, Xuyishe, Dinglin, Tsegun, and Saily (Xinli) (3rd century BC – the era of the Xiongnu ruler Modu). The Kueyishe tribe, conquered by Modu, lived in the northwestern part of the Altai. The term "Kueyishe" or "Xuyishe," first mentioned in 201 BC, is accepted by Turkologists as the first name for the Kipchaks in written sources [1, pp. 199-216]. According to many historical sources, the Kipchaks settled in the Zheliang Valley in ancient times. The name of this valley coincided with the name of the Chilyan River, which means Snake River and Snake Mountain. G.E. Grumm-Grzhimailo associated the name of the city of Zmeinogorsk with these toponyms [4, p. 59]. In the 3rd-2nd centuries BC, the Kipchaks lived in the northwestern regions of Altai. According to N.A. Aristov, in the 1st century BC and 1st century AD, individual groups of Kipchaks could have migrated from the upper reaches of the Irtysh and from areas west of Tarbagatai [2, pp. 283-290, 309, 312-

313]. From the 3rd century BC, the Kipchaks, like other Altai tribes, were part of the Huns. From the 2nd century to the 4th centuries AD, the Kipchaks were under the political domination of the Xianbei tribes, and from the end of the 4th century to the first half of the 6th century — under the political domination of the Mongol-speaking Juan Juan tribes [15, p. 19]. The Juan Juan constantly oppressed the Turkic tribes, which is why in 552 the Turkic tribes united and put an end to the Juan Juan rule. The head of the new state - the Turkic Khaganate - became Tumen (Bumyn), who took the title of Ilkhan, and in 555 the Turkic finally destroyed the Juan Juan state. Later, this title was replaced by the title of Khagan. Many Sayan-Altai tribes were included in this Khaganate. As inhabitants of Altai, the Kipchaks were also part of the Turkic Khaganate, but did not have any power in the Khaganate. For this reason, there was no information about them in ancient sources until the middle of the 7th century [15, pp. 17-19]. The Kipchaks are also mentioned in tombstone inscriptions dating back to 759–760, discovered by Gustav Ramstedt in 1909 near the Selenga River in south-central Mongolia. In literature, this epitaph was called the "Selegin Stone." This inscription is a text from a tombstone that belonged to one of the founders of the Uyghur Khaganate, Eletmish Bilge Khagan (747–759) [14, p. 134]. On the north side of the stone, in the fourth line, the following words are carved: "When the Turkic Kipchaks ruled us for fifty years..." [14, p. 145]. The renowned Arab geographer Ibn Khordadbeh (9th century, "Kitab al-masalik wa-l-mamalik" - Book of Routes and Countries) was the first explorer to identify the Kipchaks as a Turkic tribe. He presented the Kipchaks as an independent tribe living in the territory of modern-day Kazakhstan [5, pp. 64-65, 184-185].

The earliest written sources that left us with information about the Kipchaks include Arabic and Persian sources, which provide comprehensive and informative information on the history of the emergence of the Turkic ethnic group, including the Kipchaks. Among these works, the works of Arab and Persian geographers of

the 9th-13th centuries occupy a special place. Authors such as the Arab geographers Al-Masudi (10th century), Al-Istakhri (10th century), and Kitab al-masalik wa-l-mamalik (Book of Routes and Countries) wrote about the Kipchaks.

Also worth noting are such scholars as G.E. Grum-Grzhimailo, V.V. Bartold, V.F. Minorsky, N.Yu. Bichurin, S.G. Klyashtorny, S.N. Gumilev, M.I. Artamonov, N.F. Kotlyar, S.A. Pletneva, N.E. Kuzembaev, A.N. Yuzeev, A.N. Garkavets, V.V. Petrukhin, N.A. Aristov, G. Geybullaev, Z. Papasciri, M.D. Lordkipanidze, I.A. Javakhishvili, F.M. Kırzioğlu, Fuad Koprulu, Zeki Velidi Togan, and others who dedicated their works to the history of the Kipchaks.

The renowned orientalist V.V. Radlov, in his work "An Attempt at a Dictionary of Turkic Dialects," explained the following meanings of the term Kipchak.

1. The meaning of the word "Kipchak" is unclear, as it is always used with the adjective "koby" (empty). Perhaps these words have the same meaning.

2. Kipchak is an empty tree; in those days, an empty tree was called "chypchak."

3. Kipchak is an angry, crazy person [10, p. 844].

O. Suleimenov put forward the hypothesis that the ethnonym Kipchak was formed from the words "iki pchak" (eki pshak- two knives), meaning two knives. He suggests that the two horizontal lines of the tamga among the Kipchaks were once called "iki pchak" (ek pshak- two knives), and later this word, in the process of merging, turned into "Kipchak" [17, p. 146].

The vast pastures located on the shores of the Black Sea and the Sea of Azov - from the Volga to the Danube - have attracted eastern nomads since ancient times. These were successively occupied by nomadic tribal groups of the Huns (IV century), Avar and Bulgar (VI century), Khazar (VII century), Uz, Pecheneg, Turkic (IX-X centuries), Kipchaks (XI century) and Mongols (20-30s of the XIII century).

In the middle of the XI century, the Kipchaks, who had established themselves in the basins of the Volga and Don rivers, moved westward to the Dnieper steppes. Here lived the Torks (Turkic), who were the former enemies of the Kipchaks. The Torks put up strong resistance to the Kipchaks.

The advance of the Turkic's into the Dnieper steppes was not in the interests of the Kiev state. Princes Izyoslav, Svyatoslav, Vsevolod and Vseslav marched against them in 1060. Under the pressure of the Russian army, the Turkic were forced to leave the Dnieper steppes and entered the northern borders of the Byzantine Empire [7,p.214]. But some parts of the Turkic remained under the rule of the Kipchaks around the Dnieper River. With the weakening of the Turkic and their abandonment of their territories, there was no peace in the border regions of the Russian state. Other nomads, the Kipchaks, came to replace the Turkic. By the end of the 11th century, the Kipchaks had conquered vast territories of the southern Russian steppes up to the Dniester.

In the North Caucasus, there were many pastures for year-round cattle breeding. In order to conquer these lands, the Kipchak aristocrats intensified their campaigns westward in the middle of the 11th century. Most importantly, the Kipchaks sought to conquer the

Don and Black Sea steppes. The conquest of these territories provided the Kipchaks with the opportunity to control the water trade routes (Volga-Don-Dnieper) leading to the Black Sea and from there to Byzantium. The Byzantine Empire was unable to prevent the Kipchaks from advancing westward during this period, as Byzantium was embroiled in internal wars. In addition, the Byzantines were concerned about the Seljuk's movements in Asia Minor.

The vast pastures along the shores of the Black and Azov Seas - from the Volga to the Danube - have attracted eastern nomads since ancient times. They were successively occupied by the nomadic tribes of the Huns (4th century), Avars and Bulgars (6th century), Khazars (7th century), Uz, Pechenegs, Turkic (9th-10th centuries), Kipchaks (11th century), and Mongols (1220s-1230s).

2. Kipchaks in the Caucasus

In the middle 11th century, the Kipchaks, who had settled in the Volga and Don basins, moved westward into the Dnieper steppes. This was inhabited by the Torks (Turkic), former enemies of the Kipchaks. The Torks offered fierce resistance to the Kipchaks. The advance of the Torks into the Dnieper steppes did not serve the interests of the Kievan state. In 1060, the princes Izyoslav, Svyatoslav, Vsevolod, and Vseslav rebelled against them. Under pressure from the Russian army, the Turkic were forced to abandon the Dnieper steppes and enter the northern borders of the Byzantine Empire [7,p.214]. However, some Turkic remained under Kipchak rule in the Dnieper region. With the weakening of the Turkic and their abandonment of their territories, there was no peace in the border regions of the Russian state. The Turkic were replaced by other nomads - the Kipchaks. By the end of the 11th century, the Kipchaks had conquered vast territories of the southern Russian steppes, reaching as far as the Dniester.

The North Caucasus offered abundant pastures for year-round livestock raising. To conquer these lands, the Kipchak aristocracy intensified its campaigns westward in the middle 11th century. The Kipchaks primarily sought to conquer the Don and Black Sea steppes. The conquest of these territories gave the Kipchaks control over the water trade routes (Volga-Don-Dnieper) leading to the Black Sea and from there to Byzantium. The Byzantine Empire was unable to prevent the Kipchaks' westward advance during this period, as Byzantium was engulfed in internal wars. Furthermore, the Byzantines were concerned about Seljuk movements in Asia Minor.

K.V. Kudryashov established that at the end of the 11th-12th centuries, the Kipchak-Poloves occupied the territories located around the Black Sea and on the shores of the Sea of Azov [8,p.123]. The Kipchaks also migrated to the steppes of the Fore Caucasus and the banks of the Lower Volga and Yaik rivers. The northern part of the Kipchak lands adjoined the southeastern steppes of the Kiev state. This northern part, starting from the mouth of the Danube, covered the lower reaches of the Dniester and Southern Bug rivers, the lower reaches of the Vistula, the Tyasmin River, and the Chnu River. The eastern part of the Polovtsian lands

adjoined the southern borders of the Kama Bulgars. These territories reached the Caspian Sea [8, p. 146].

One group of the Kipchaks lived near the lower Volga. Their habitation in the southern Russian steppes is also evidenced by numerous burial mounds found by archaeologists in the territories from the Dniester to the Volga [9, p. 172]. A certain part of the Kipchaks also lived in the North Caucasus in the 11th-13th centuries. They arrived here approximately in the 60s-70s of the 11th century.

The main areas of Kipchak migrations in the North Caucasus were considered its central part. Their capital was the city of Sunzhe, located on the banks of the Sunzha River. Archaeological data also confirm the habitation of the Kipchaks in these territories in the 11th-13th centuries. The southern border of the Kipchaks' distribution areas in the North Caucasus passed along the Ar-mavir-Pyatigorsk-Kalmyk steppes. The Kipchaks also lived in the coastal areas of Dagestan.

There are many sources about the settlement of the Turkic tribes in Azerbaijan and in Western Asia as a whole in the 14th-15th centuries. This was shown most accurately by the author of the work "The Book of Knowledge of the World" John de Galonifontibus (1404) during his journey to the Caucasus [6, http://ap-snyteka.org/809galonifontibus_ioann_de_kniga_poznaniya_mira.html]. In the chapter entitled "Tats and Goths. Great Tartary: Kumania, Khazaria and others. Peoples of the Caucasus" he wrote about the composition, religion and spread of the Turkic language among the Caucasian peoples: "In this country there are many Christians, namely: Greeks, Ziks, Goths, Tats, Volyaks, Russians, Circassians, Leks, Yasses, Alans, Avars, Kazikumukhs and almost all of them speak the Tatar language." The term "Tatar language" denoted a Turkic lang"age.

The Volyaks (Valani in German, Comani in Latin, Polovtsy in Russian;"their real name was Kipchaks) lived in the North Caucasus [6, http://ap-snyteka.org/809galonifontibus_ioann_de_kniga_poznaniya_mira.html].

In the early 11th-13th centuries, separate groups of Kipchaks also lived in Azerbaijan. They were initially brought here as slaves and captives. The presence of Kipchaks in Azerbaijan is evidenced by the existence of the village of Kipchak in the Gakh region, which is associated with the name of these tribes, and the Kipchak Pass in the Kelbajar region [3, pp. 41-45].

Z. M. Buniyatov believed that the Kipchaks invaded Albania as early as the 7th century [13, pp. 123-124].

Some toponyms in Azerbaijan, such as Kazakh, Kazakhlu, and Kazakhlar, are associated with the Kipchaks. G. A. Geybullaev believed that the Kipchak origin of the Kazakhs is also confirmed by the oikonym Kaymakly (Kazakh region), which reflects the ethnonym kaymak/kimak [3, pp. 41-46]. There are many Kipchak ethnonyms in the Kakh region. One of the Kipchak ethnonyms was "Terter". According to G. A. Geybullaev, this ethnonym arose in Azerbaijan before the Kipchaks appeared in the southern Russian steppes, which suggests that some of them stayed among the Huns [3, pp. 41-45]. Also in the toponymy of Azerbai-

jan, one can find "Tug" (Karabakh) and Tugchay (Absheron region). The toponyms uran, andja or inji, jujan, urus or arus, kuch, durt or turut, kul, katan (kotan), and karaberk left their mark on the toponymy of Azerbaijan. G. Geybullayev believed that the Kipchaks penetrated Azerbaijan during different historical periods, approximately from the 7th to the 12th centuries [3, pp. 41-45]. Therefore, the Kipchaks played a certain role in the ethnic process that led to the formation of the Azerbaijani people [3, pp. 41-45].

Many words in the Azerbaijani language also originate from Turkic-Kipchak words. Taking this into account, linguist M.Sh. Shiraliyev writes: "As is known, beginning in the 5th century, individual Turkic languages of the Kipchak type were present in the northern part of Azerbaijan, which played an important role in the formation of the Azerbaijani vernacular." In the northern and, to some extent, eastern group of dialects and subdialects of the Azerbaijani language, Kipchak features are still clearly evident. The task of Azerbaijani dialectologists is to identify the Kipchak elements preserved in the phonetics, vocabulary, and grammar of the Azerbaijani language" [12, p. 6].

Shamseddin Eldaniz, the founder of the Eldaniz dynasty in Azerbaijan, was also of Kipchak origin. Eldaniz served in the Seljuk army, which was made up of slaves. He attracted the attention of the Seljuk nobles with his bravery and began to serve under Masud Khan. In 1143, Eldaniz was given the territory of Iran and Azerbaijan. After 40 years, the Seljuk dynasty in Iran was destroyed. Eldaniz's son Jahan Pahlavan and his grandson Uzbek preserved these lands. The Eldaniz dynasty existed in Azerbaijan until 1225, and their capital was Tabriz.

An unknown Georgian historian, in his work describing the reign of David IV (1089-1125), called these Kipchaks "Derbend Kipchaks"[1, p. 125]. Georgian sources also report Kipchaks in Transcaucasia from 456 to 510, but the mass migration occurred in connection with the events of the 12th century. In 1118-1120, David IV the Builder resettled 225,000 North Caucasian Kipchaks to Georgia, led by their leader Khan Atrak, married his daughter, and, with the help of the Kipchaks, created a strong army. Later, George III (1151-1184) resettled approximately 10,000 Kipchaks to Georgia [16, pp. 236-237].

The Georgian king David IV sent an envoy to the daughter of the Kipchak Khan Atrak. Georgian sources called Atrak Khan's daughter Qurandokta (originally Turandokt). This means "Turanli daughter", "Turan daughter". David IV recruited 40 thousand selected warriors from the Kipchaks for his army and 5 thousand warriors for his personal guard. Relying on this strength, David IV broke the resistance of the Georgian feudal lords and switched from defense to attack in his foreign policy. Thus, in 1120, he crushed the Turkic-speaking nomadic tribes under the rule of the Seljuk sultans who had entered the southern and southeastern provinces of Georgia. The resettlement of Kipchaks to Georgia continued in subsequent periods.

During the reign of George III (1151-1184), tens of thousands of Kipchaks and Ossetians were also resettled here. It should be noted that during the reign of Tamara (1184-1213), the term "new Kipchaks" existed

